

Survey: Information Technology Governance in Colombian Enterprises

Introduction

This survey seeks to establish a Colombia-wide study on the state of IT management and governance in organizations and is based on ISACA's Governance of Enterprise IT (GEIT) Survey. The data is used for academic purposes. It is directed to graduate students related to Information Technology from different universities in Colombia. The survey is divided into 3 sections: 1. Characterization of the Organization. 2. IT Strategic Alignment. 3. IT Projections and Incidents in the organization. Some of the data from this survey is used for postgraduate academic purposes for the Master's Degree in IT Management.

Informed Consent Statement

In 2019, when the survey was designed, it was not mandatory to include the endorsement of the ethics committee for surveys at the Universidad Cooperativa de Colombia. The guidelines of the Colombian public policy were followed, which is established with the purpose of guaranteeing and respecting the privacy of personal data on which the authors perform treatment and to fully comply with the parameters established in article 15 of the political constitution of Colombia, the law 1587 of 2012, the regulatory decrees 1377 of 2013 and 886 of 2014 - today incorporated in chapters 25 and 26 of the single decree 1074 of 2015 and the other rules that regulate it. For data confidentiality issues, the name of the organization (optional).

Section 1. Organizational Characterization

1. Name and surname (optional) **(Input Text)**
2. Name of organization or company where you work (optional) **(Input Text)**
3. Which of the following positions is closest to your level of work? **(Single Choice)**
 - Analyst
 - Professional
 - Supervisor
 - Manager
 - Director
 - Vice President
 - President/CEO
 - External Consultant
 - Academic
 - Intern
4. What is your education (professional degree)? **(Input Text)**
5. Specific position in the organization **(Input Text)**
6. How many people are employed in your company, including all branches, divisions and subsidiaries.
 - 0-10
 - 10-50
 - 50-250
 - Over 250
7. The company or organization to which you belong is of order:
 - International
 - Local/Regional

- National
- 8. City of location of the Company (main office). **(Input Text)**
- 9. Origin of the capital of the organization or company is:
 - Private
 - Public
 - Mixed
- 10. Choose any of the following to determine in which sector the organization or company is located. **(Single Choice)**
 - Industrial / Commercial
 - Technology Services
 - Government
 - Education
 - Goods and Services
 - Health

Section 2. IT strategic alignment

1. Is there an IT department or management in the organization? **(Single Choice)**
 - Yes
 - No
2. How important does your company's executive team consider information and technology to your company's strategy and vision? **(Single Choice)**
 - Very Important
 - Not Very Important.
 - Don't Know
3. How would you describe the level of involvement of the company's management in the company's IT governance? **(Single Choice)**
 - High
 - Low
 - Moderate
 - Uncertain
4. What is the greatest benefit your organization receives from its IT investments? **(Single Choice)**
 - Improved customer service.
 - New or improved products and services.
 - Cost reduction.
 - Improved business intelligence.
 - Improved information security.
 - All the above.
 - Not applicable.
5. Over the next 12 months, what does your organization plan to do with respect to IT-related investments? **(Single Choice)**
 - Selective growth based on potential/expected contribution to business value
 - Uncertain
 - Generalized increase
 - Reduce across the board

- Freeze at current level
- Reduce selectively based on potential/expected contribution to business value.
- Don't know.
- Other

Section 3. IT Projections and Incidents in the Organization.

1. Current use of emerging and new technology to support processes **(Multiple Choice)**
 - Data Mining.
 - Business Intelligence.
 - Big Data.
 - Artificial Intelligence.
 - Virtual Reality / Augmented Reality.
 - Social Networking.
 - Robotics/ Process Automation.
 - Others
 - None

2. Which of the following technologies does your organization plan to implement in the short to medium term? **(Multiple Choice)**
 - Data Mining.
 - Business Intelligence.
 - Big Data.
 - Artificial Intelligence.
 - Virtual Reality / Augmented Reality.
 - Social Networking.
 - Robotics/ Process Automation.
 - Others
 - None

3. Which of the following has your company experienced (even for a short period of time) in the last 12 months because of an IT-related problem/incident? **(Multiple Choice)**
 - Incurring unexpected expenses.
 - Reputation was damaged.
 - Customer satisfaction was reduced.
 - Cost reduction opportunities were delayed or lost.
 - A competitor beat my company to market.
 - None.
 - Other.

4. Briefly Explain the Case(s) (optional) **(Multiple Choice)**

5. Does your company use a framework/standard for governance and management/governance/ EA or IT services?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Don't know.

6. If yes, which framework/standard is used? **(Multiple Choice)**
 - ITIL
 - TOGAF
 - ZACHMAN
 - CMMI

- ISO
 - OTHER
7. Which of the following problems has your company experienced in the last 12 months? Select at least the 3 most relevant **(Multiple Choice)**
- High IT cost with low or unknown return on investment.
 - Project cost overruns.
 - Security breaches.
 - Inadequate IT staffing.
 - Inadequate disaster recovery or business continuity measures.
 - Lack of innovation.
 - Serious IT operation incidents.
 - Outsourcing issue.
 - None.
 - Other.
 - Don't know
8. In the next 12 months, what is the most likely issue to challenge your organization's network security? **(Multiple Choice)**
- Incidents related to employees' personal devices.
 - Cyber-attacks.
 - External hacking.
 - Data leakage.
 - Unintentional employee errors.
 - Disgruntled employee.
 - All of the above.
 - None of the above.
 - Other.
9. Has your organization recently terminated or cancelled an IT-related project before it has been fully implemented? **(Single Choice)**
- Yes
 - No
 - Don't know
- If yes to the above answer, please select the reason why.
- Changes in business needs.
 - Failed to deliver what was promised.
 - Exceeded budget.
 - Did not support business strategy.
 - No other reason for cancellation.
 - Other Reasons for cancellation
10. After analyzing your answers, develop a reflection around the strategic alignment of IT in your organization. **(Input Text)**